

30 vocalisations was higher near the *pedrizas*. This result was not due to differences in
31 species richness, so it supports the prediction of the hypothesis. This is new evidence that
32 birds might use a natural element within their habitat to increase sound transmission.

33 **Keywords:** Bird communication; sound transmission; rocky ground; Mediterranean
34 forest; natural soundscape.

35 **Introduction**

36 Vocalisations (songs and calls) are communicative signals that are used by birds to
37 transmit information (Catchpole and Slater 2008). Mate attraction, territorial defence or
38 warning signals are functions of bird acoustic communication (Catchpole and Slater,
39 2008; Pärckert, 2018; Riebel *et al.*, 2019). Despite the advantages in the evolutionary
40 context of their functions, songs and calls might also imply costs regarding energy
41 expenditure and detection by predators (Catchpole and Slater, 2008; Ward and Slater,
42 2005). It is expected that birds produce sounds when their advantages outweigh costs.
43 Therefore, the number of discrete vocalisations produced by birds might depend on the
44 presence of potential mates, competitors or predators, as well as physical properties such
45 as the acoustic transmission of the habitats.

46 Information conveyed in bird vocalisations may be hindered by habitat features. Habitat
47 complexity or noisy environments can modify signals and reduce their communicative
48 function (Catchpole and Slater, 2008; Barker *et al.*, 2009; Halfwerk *et al.*, 2018). Birds
49 might use different strategies to avoid the loss of information, and they are able to match
50 their songs and calls to the acoustic properties of the habitat (Hansen, 1979). For instance,
51 Brumm (2004) found that nightingales (*Luscinia megarhynchos*) sing louder in noisy
52 areas than in quieter ones. Nicholls and Goldizen (2006) found that habitat type influences

53 variation in the advertisement calls of the satin bowerbirds (*Ptilonorhynchus violaceus*),
54 being transmission qualities of habitats the main determinant of the effect.

55 One of the main problems for the transmission of a bird sound is that of attenuation (Wiley
56 and Richards, 1978). The signal intensity decreases with distance from the source (Fang
57 and Ling, 2005). However, there are other factors that produce attenuation and, hence,
58 hinder the transmission of bird sounds (Bass, 1991). Habitat characteristics such as
59 vegetation structure can influence the transmission of vocalisations (Proppe *et al.*, 2010;
60 Nasiri *et al.*, 2015). For instance, dense foliage increases attenuation (Martens 1980;
61 Blumenrath and Dabelsteen, 2004). In order to promote sound transmission, birds use
62 different strategies such as singing on perches high in the vegetation (Catchpole and
63 Slater, 2008; Barker *et al.*, 2009). Some studies show that the benefits of long-distance
64 transmission are more relevant to the birds than the benefits of advertising performance
65 ability or the costs of song production (Benedict and Warning, 2017).

66 The Mediterranean forest includes an important community of animals and plants (Myers
67 *et al.*, 2000). Climax vegetation has been restricted to certain areas due to the strong
68 pressure exerted by human activities for many centuries. In central-western Spain, the
69 most conserved Mediterranean forests are found mainly on quartzite mountainous areas
70 where large steep stones are frequent. Within the forest there are some areas without
71 vegetation forming scree slopes of quartzite origin, known in Spain as *pedrizas* (see
72 Figure 1). These fragmented rocks were produced during the Quaternary period by a
73 gelifraction process (Pulido-Fernández *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, a typical habitat in many
74 mountain ranges of south and central western Spain is a Mediterranean forest in which
75 there are areas covered by *pedrizas*.

76 The acoustic properties of these scree slopes differ from those in the surrounding forest.
77 The presence of rocky surfaces predominates in *pedrizas*, has high acoustic impedance
78 and can be considered mainly as acoustically reflective or hard surfaces in the terms
79 indicated by the ISO standards (ISO 9613-2, 1996; ISO 1996-2, 2017). Therefore, when
80 the sound waves reach these types of surfaces, a high percentage of the sound energy is
81 reflected. In contrast, some elements present in the forest, such as bare earth and forest
82 mass, contribute to sound attenuation (Bucur, 2006; Swearingen *et al.*, 2013). The lower
83 attenuation of bird sound on reflective surfaces has been shown in previous studies (Yip
84 *et al.*, 2017). In addition, *pedrizas* are found in open spaces, thus being unaffected by
85 other factors that affect the propagation and clarity of bird vocalisations, such as
86 reverberation (Gogoleva, 2018).

87 Vegetation mass is expected to attenuate sounds and hinder bird communication in the
88 Mediterranean forest. However, areas with *pedrizas* could favour the transmission of
89 information. Consequently, the effect of *pedrizas* on sound transmission should be higher
90 when birds' vocalisations are emitted on the *pedrizas* and this effect should decrease as
91 the distance of birds' vocalisations from *pedrizas* increases. It was therefore hypothesized
92 that birds might use scree slopes to promote sound propagation and, hence, to increase
93 the transmission of their vocalisations. This hypothesis is not tested in this study.
94 However, the following prediction of the hypothesis was assessed: if birds actively use
95 scree slopes to promote sound transmission, the frequency of vocalisations recorded near
96 the *pedrizas* should be higher than in forest areas far away from *pedrizas*.

97 A high number of vocalisations recorded near the *pedrizas* might be due to processes
98 different to those related to sound transmission. *Pedrizas* might ecologically influence
99 bird distribution. In this case, a high number of vocalisations near *pedrizas* would be due

100 to the biased distribution of bird biodiversity. The relationship between the distance to
101 *pedrizas* and bird biodiversity is a necessary control to assess the prediction of the
102 hypothesis. The lack of this relationship supports that a high number of vocalisations
103 recorded near *pedrizas* can be due to processes related to sound transmission.

104 The prediction of the hypothesis was assessed in the Mediterranean forest of Monfragüe
105 National Park located in central-western Spain. Here it was found that the frequency of
106 vocalisation was higher the closer the sampling point was to *pedrizas* as expected by the
107 prediction. However, there were not more bird species near the *pedrizas*. This work
108 constitutes a starting point for future studies to test the proposed hypothesis.

109 **Material and methods**

110 The study was carried out in a highly conserved Mediterranean forest in Monfragüe
111 National Park. This forest is composed of cork oaks (*Quercus suber*) and several scrub
112 species such as strawberry tree (*Arbutus unedo*), laurustinus (*Viburnum tinus*), myrtle
113 (*Mirtus communis*), false olive (*Phillyrea angustifolia*) and heaths (*Erica* spp.). *Pedrizas*
114 are frequent in this area.

115 To record bird sounds, a portable Zoom H6 recorder was used with Roland Binaural
116 microphones. The recorder was located at 9 points in Monfragüe at different distances to
117 three *pedrizas* (Figure 1). Sampling locations were in a forest patch with the same
118 vegetation species composition and the same Northern orientation. The size the *pedrizas*
119 are 3450.63 m² (*pedriza* of point 2), 3342.04 m² (*pedriza* of point 4) and 5886.85 m²
120 (*pedriza* of point 6).

121 Recordings were collected on February 28th, 2020. Bird vocalizations were recorded
122 during 5 minutes at each sampling point. The first recording started at 11:30 a.m. and the

123 remaining recordings were conducted consecutively. The last recording ended at 13:00
124 p.m. During recordings temperature was 15 ° C, sun and clouds, wind speed = 5 km/h).

125 All the vocalisations of the different bird species were identified in the recordings. The
126 analysis and management of recordings were performed using the free software Sonic
127 Visualiser (<https://www.sonicvisualiser.org/>) and Audacity
128 (<https://www.audacityteam.org/>). Species identification was conducted mainly aurally by
129 the authors' experience, although the visual inspection of spectrograms helped in the
130 process. Doubts were managed with the help of the Birdnet web page
131 (<https://birdnet.cornell.edu/api/>). A small proportion of vocalisations could not be
132 identified as belonging to a specific species (see results). Unidentified vocalisations were
133 removed from subsequent analyses.

134 From each recording, the number of recorded vocalisations produced by each bird species
135 was counted. In addition to the number of vocalisations, the other important variable in
136 our study was the distance of each vocalisation to the *pedrizas*. The distance of a
137 vocalisation to the *pedrizas* was quantified by averaging the distances from the sampling
138 point where the vocalisation was recorded to the centroids of the three *pedrizas*.

139 For each bird species, the number of vocalisations and the distance to *pedrizas* of each
140 vocalisation were registered. The difference between the distance to the *pedrizas* of the
141 vocalisations and the averaged distance to *pedrizas* of all sampling points (0.298 km) was
142 assessed with one sample T-test for each species and across species.

143 To assess the prediction of the hypothesis, the relationship between the distance of the
144 sampling points to *pedrizas* and the number of recorded vocalisations was determined. A
145 Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) fitted by maximum likelihood with Poisson
146 distribution was conducted. For this model, the number of vocalisations was included as

147 the explanatory variable, the distance to *pedrizas* as fixed factor, and sampling location
148 as random factor. In order to assess the effect of zero-inflation, the model was repeated
149 after removing zero values.

150 Species richness in the recordings was used as an estimate of bird biodiversity. Species
151 richness was a presence-absence binomial variable and was obtained after transforming
152 the variable number of vocalisations. Zero value was assigned to species for which no
153 vocalisations were recorded, and 1 value to species for which, at least, one vocalisation
154 was recorded. Therefore, to determine the relationship between the distance to *pedrizas*
155 and bird biodiversity, a GLMM fitted by maximum likelihood with binomial distribution
156 was conducted with the presence-absence variable (species richness) as the explanatory
157 variable, the distance to *pedrizas* as fixed factor, and sampling location as random factor.

158 GLMMs were performed with *lme4* package (Bates *et al.*, 2015) in R software (R Core
159 Team, 2019). Model residuals were checked for heteroscedasticity by using residual plots.
160 No signs of heteroscedasticity were found. Spatial analyses were conducted with QGIS
161 (QGIS.org 2021).

162 **Results**

163 The averaged distance of each sampling point to the centroids of the *pedrizas* was 0.280
164 km (point 1 in Figure 1), 0.197 km (point 2), 0.205 km (point 3), 0.161 (point 4), 0.204
165 km (point 5), 0.243 km (point 6), 0.396 km (point 7), 0.497 km (point 8), and 0.495 km
166 (point 9). The mean number of recorded vocalisations per minute was 27.93 and 7.3 % of
167 vocalisations were not identified. Unidentified vocalisations corresponded to short calls
168 that were determined neither by authors nor the Birdnet web page. We identified 20 bird
169 species in the recordings (Table 1). Table 1 also shows the number of vocalisations from
170 each species and across all species, as well as the mean distance of the recorded

171 vocalisation to the centroids of *pedrizas*. The mean distance to *pedrizas* of vocalisations
172 tended to be lower than the averaged distance to *pedrizas* of all sampling points for several
173 species (Table 1, Figure 2). However, the mean distance to *pedrizas* across all species
174 was lower than the mean distance to *pedrizas* of all sampling points (Table 1, Figure 2).

175 The number of recorded vocalisations was negatively associated with the distance to the
176 *pedrizas* (Table 2, Figure 3). This result was obtained when all data were used (Table 2a,
177 Figure 3) and after removing zero values (Table 2b, Figure 3). Despite the general trend
178 we found in our data, there was one species (*Certhia brachydactyla*) to which we recorded
179 high numbers of vocalisations far away from *pedrizas* (Table 1, Figure 2, and high
180 number of vocalisations at high distance to *pedrizas* in Figure 3).

181 Despite the number of vocalisations was negatively associated with the distance to
182 *pedrizas*, no relationship was found between the distance to *pedrizas* and species richness.
183 (Table 3). The lower distance to *pedrizas* was not related to an increase in the number of
184 bird species obtained in the recordings.

185 **Discussion**

186 In the Mediterranean forest of Monfragüe National Park, the number of vocalisations
187 recorded near the *pedrizas* was higher than in forest areas far away from *pedrizas*. The
188 results support a prediction of the hypothesis that birds might actively use scree slopes to
189 promote sound transmission.

190 In our study, the relationship between the distance to *pedrizas* and bird biodiversity is a
191 necessary control to assess the prediction of the hypothesis. The distance to *pedrizas* was
192 not related to the estimated bird biodiversity. This result supports that *pedrizas* could not
193 ecologically determine bird biodiversity. Factors related to resource availability or

194 predation risk could not promote the presence of birds near *pedrizas*. Therefore, the high
195 number of vocalisations recorded near *pedrizas* might be due to a better transmission of
196 sound on scree slopes.

197 Signal transmission is particularly conditioned by the propagation of sound in the
198 environment (Winkler, 2001). Birds use different strategies to favour sound transmission:
199 the wren (*Troglodytes troglodytes*) chooses higher song posts (Barker et al. 2009), male
200 blue-black grassquits (*Volatinia jacarina*) leap vertically above the dense grass
201 (Wilczynski *et al.*, 1989) and male bluethroats (*Luscinia svecica*) sing in flight (Sorjonen
202 and Merilä, 2000; Catchpole and Slater, 2008). Studies taking into account sound
203 frequencies found different behavioural strategies depending on ecological conditions
204 (Boncoraglio and Saino, 2007; Ey and Fischer, 2009). The great tit produces sounds with
205 a lower maximum frequency and frequency range in forests than in open woodland
206 (Hunter and Krebs, 1979). The little greenbul (*Andropadus virens*) varies its minimum
207 frequencies across a rainforest gradient in Africa (Slabbekoorn and Smith, 2002). The
208 tinamou (*Eudromia elegans*) increases its vocal amplitude in response to the increase in
209 background noise (Schuster *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, woodpeckers hammer their bills
210 rapidly against a resonating substrate to communicate, hard surfaces (dead trees) being
211 preferred by individuals (Miles *et al.*, 2018). The selection of dead trees might help to
212 increase sound intensity. The hypothesis of this study would be proposed as a strategy in
213 which birds might actively use a natural element within their habitat to favour sound
214 transmission.

215 We found a general trend based on all the species for which we recorded vocalisations in
216 the Mediterranean forest of Monfragüe National Park. Low sample sizes and the
217 performing of multiple comparisons hinder the obtaining of conclusions at species level.
218 However, it could be expected that the hypothesis proposed in this work might be

219 particularly important in some species. For instance, frequent species such as the common
220 chaffinch (*Fringilla coelebs*) or the blue tit (*Cyanistes caeruleus*) seem to follow the
221 general pattern we found across all species. In the same way, the hypothesis might not
222 work for other species. For instance, we found a high number of vocalisations of the short-
223 toed treecreeper (*Certhia brachydactyla*) in a sampling point far away from *pedrizas*. This
224 sampling point was characterized to the presence of a water spring, and water resources
225 determines the presence and distribution of birds in Monfragüe National Park (Pérez-
226 González J, Rey Gozalo G, Montes González D, Hidalgo de Trucios S, Barrigón Morillas
227 JM, unpublished data). Different acoustic and biological features might determine for
228 which species is important the effect of scree slopes in sound transmission.

229 The use by a bird species of natural elements within its habitat in the context proposed in
230 this work could open lines of future research. Individuals might use these elements as
231 “instruments” favouring sound transmission. Each habitat includes an exclusive set of
232 natural elements and the home range of a bird species might include different habitats.
233 Therefore, different populations of the same species might use specific elements within
234 their habitats to favour sound transmission. This approach might imply the existence of
235 cultural behaviours in birds, as previously proposed in traits related to dialects (Luther
236 and Baptista, 2010).

237 This work may be used as a starting point for future studies on the modulation of bird
238 behaviour depending on habitat features such as the presence of scree slopes. These future
239 studies should be conducted by using experimental designs or the collection of large
240 amounts of data. Both approaches require an intense effort that might be justified by the
241 findings of this study. Despite the assessment of possible bias related to the distance of
242 transmission for bird vocalisations, the high sound transmission on scree slopes or the

243 different habitat quality, they should be considered to design experiments or data
244 collection. The use of scree slopes with bigger surfaces, the assessing of mean territory
245 size of the recorded bird species, the counting of individuals and the use of call rates, or
246 the registering of the time spent by individuals singing on *pedrizas* or in the surrounding
247 forest could also help to control all possible biases.

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263 **Disclosure statement**

264 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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360 **Table 1.** Vocalisations from each bird species and across all species. Table shows the
361 number and rate of recorded vocalisations, as well as the mean and standard error of the
362 distance to *pedrizas* of the vocalisations. Table also shows the *p* values of the one sample
363 T test for the difference between the mean distance to *pedrizas* of vocalisations and the
364 mean distance to *pedrizas* of all sampling points (0.298 km). Standard error (SE) of
365 distance equals 0 when all vocalisations were recorded in the same sampling point, so
366 there was not variance in distance to *pedrizas*. ND: there are not enough data to obtain
367 the parameter or to conduct the analysis. ND in SE distance was obtained when there was
368 only one vocalisation. ND in *p* values was obtained when there was not SE of the distance
369 to *pedrizas* of vocalisations.

Species	Number of vocalisations	Vocalisations per minute	Mean distance	SE distance	<i>p</i>
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	470	10.444	0.213	0.002	<0.001
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i>	194	4.311	0.382	0.009	<0.001
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	188	4.178	0.218	0.007	<0.001
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i>	130	2.889	0.311	0.012	0.262
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	70	1.556	0.243	0	ND
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	43	0.956	0.204	0	ND
<i>Sitta europaea</i>	40	0.889	0.497	0	ND
<i>Sylvia cantillans</i>	22	0.489	0.161	0	ND
<i>Parus major</i>	18	0.400	0.249	0.015	0.005
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>	17	0.378	0.253	0.034	0.209
<i>Lullula arborea</i>	16	0.356	0.396	0	ND
<i>Periparus ater</i>	14	0.311	0.261	0.005	<0.001
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	12	0.267	0.327	0.030	0.352
<i>Turdus merula</i>	8	0.178	0.283	0.044	0.760

<i>Carduelis spinus</i>	5	0.111	0.495	0	ND
<i>Serinus serinus</i>	3	0.067	0.495	0	ND
<i>Carduelis cannabina</i>	3	0.067	0.352	0.072	0.530
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i>	2	0.044	0.243	0	ND
<i>Sylvia melanocephala</i>	1	0.022	0.243	ND	ND
<i>Chloris chloris</i>	1	0.022	0.204	ND	ND
Across all species	1257	27.933	0.267	0.003	<0.001

370

371 **Table 2.** Relationship between the mean distance to *pedrizas* of vocalisations and the
 372 number of recorded vocalisations. Results from the GLMM with the number of
 373 vocalisations as the explanatory variable, mean distance to *pedrizas* as fixed factor, and
 374 sampling location as random factor. A) GLMM using all data. B) GLMM after removing
 375 zero values. SD: standard deviation.

A) Term	Estimate	SE	Variance	SD	z	p
Fixed factors						
Intercept	3.083	0.715			4.313	<0.001
Distance to <i>pedrizas</i>	-4.911	2.241			-2.191	0.028
Random factor						
Sampling location			0.657	0.811		
B) Term	Estimate	SE	Variance	SD	z	p
Fixed factors						
Intercept	4.577	0.501			9.129	<0.001
Distance to <i>pedrizas</i>	-5.209	1.586			-3.285	0.001
Random factor						
Sampling location			0.317	0.563		

376

377 **Table 3.** Relationship between the mean distance to *pedrizas* of vocalisations and species
 378 richness. Results from the GLMM with species richness (presence-absence binomial
 379 variable) as the dependent variable, mean distance to *pedrizas* as fixed factor, and
 380 sampling location as random factor.

A) Term	Estimate	SE	Variance	SD	z	p
Fixed factors						
Intercept	-1.189	0.499			-2.382	0.017
Distance to <i>pedrizas</i>	1.000	1.530			0.414	0.679
Random factor						
Sampling location			0.071	0.267		

381

382 **Figure 1. A)** Location of Monfragüe National Park. **B)** Study area in Monfragüe National
383 Park. Numbers indicate the location of sampling points. Black points: sampling points at
384 a distance from the *pedrizas*. Grey points: sampling points on one of the three *pedrizas*
385 included in this study. **C)** View of a quartzite scree slope or *pedriza*.

387 **Figure 2.** Distance to *pedrizas* of vocalisations recorded for each species and across all
 388 species. Boxplots were performed for the species with highest number of vocalisations
 389 and with variance in the distance to *pedrizas* (Fc: *Fringilla coelebs*; Cb: *Certhia*
 390 *brachydactyla*; Cc: *Cyanistes caeruleus*; Ac: *Aegithalos caudatus*; Pm: *Parus major*; Sa:
 391 *Sylvia atricapilla*; Pa: *Periparus ater*; Er: *Erithacus rubecula*; Tm: *Turdus merula*; All:
 392 across all species). Distance to *pedrizas* was quantified by averaging the distance of each
 393 vocalisation to the centroids of the three *pedrizas*. Horizontal dotted line: mean distance
 394 to *pedrizas* of all sampling points.

395

396 **Figure 3.** Relationship between distance to *pedrizas* and number of recorded
397 vocalisations. Observed values are represented with jitter points to handling overplotting.
398 Black line: model prediction with all data (see Table 2a). Grey line: model prediction
399 after removing zero values (see Table 2b).

400